

MARVIC
MRV for carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

Glossary for Carbon Farming

Document information

Grant agreement	101112942
Project title	Developing and testing a framework for the design of harmonized, context-specific Monitoring, Reporting and Verification systems for soil Carbon and greenhouse gas balances by agricultural activities
Project acronym	MARVIC
Project duration	48 months
Coordinator	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), Belgium
Related work package(s)	WP1
Lead organisation	Agrosolutions
Author(s)	Roxane PHOTINODELLIS (Agrosolutions), Lorette LORAND (Agrosolutions), Edouard LANCKRIET (Agrosolutions), Flora DESMET (WBF), Fenny VAN EGMOND (WR), Chantal HENDRIKS (WR), Marta BERTOLA (UCSC), Karina MARQUES (EMS), Tristano BACCHETTI DE GREGORIS (SAE), Sofia BIFFI (AU), Iris VOGELER (AU), Katarina ELOFSSON (AU), Martin THORSØE (AU), Eric CESCHIA (INRAE), Liisa KULMALA (FMI), Layla HÖCKERSTEDT (FMI), Istem FER (FMI), Eric CESCHIA (INRAE), Manuel MARTIN (INRAE), Gianni BELLOCCHI (INRAE), Laure Bamière (INRAE), Silvia CODERONI (UNITE), Diana Escobar (UNITE), Berit Hasler (UCPH), Hui XU (ILVO), Greet RUYSSCHAERT (ILVO)
Contributors	MARVIC consortium
Dissemination level	Public

Document revision history

Date	Version	Submitted by	Reviewed by
30/07/2025	1.0	Agrosolutions	MARVIC Consortium
29/05/2026	2.0	Agrosolutions	MARVIC Consortium

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20341020

How to cite this Glossary:

MARVIC consortium (2026). MARVIC Glossary for Carbon Farming (part of MARVIC Deliverable 1.3 Draft MRV framework, v2.0; p10). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20341020>

Disclaimer

MARVIC Glossary v2.0 is part of MARVIC deliverable D1.3 *Draft MRV framework* reflects only the authors' views and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. **Please note that this deliverable has not yet been approved by the European Commission and is still under review.**

Note: This is a first proposition. Feedback and discussion are welcome.

Project consortium

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	ILVO	BE
ILMATIETEEN LAITOS	FMI	FI
STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE	UCSC	IT
CITIMAP SOCIETA CONSORTILE A RL	CITIMAP	IT
SOLUCIONES AGRICOLAS ECOINNOVADORAS	SAE	ES
CESKA ZEMEDELSKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE	CZU	CZ
AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	ES
AARHUS UNIVERSITET	AU	DK
TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY	TEAGASC	IE
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	FR
EESTI MAAULIKOOL	EMU	EE
ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG	ALU-FR	DE
AGROSOLUTIONS	AGROSOLUT IONS	FR
UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN	UCPH	DK
UNIVERISTY OF TERAMO	UNITE	IT
EIDGENOESSISCHES DEPARTEMENT FUER WIRTSCHAFT, BILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG	WBF	CH
Esférico MRV Systems	EMS	ES

Executive Summary

The field of carbon farming is a rapidly evolving domain characterized by its complexity and the challenges associated with establishing a shared, consensual vocabulary. Terms often hold different meanings for different stakeholders, and conversely, various terminologies may be used to describe the same concept. Moreover, consensus on the definitions behind certain terms is sometimes entirely absent.

In MARVIC, the need for a glossary quickly emerged to address these challenges and clarify the use of terms across multidisciplinary fields in carbon farming. This glossary was developed collaboratively by consortium members to align on key terms and concepts. It is a living document, updated as the field evolves, and primarily serves communication among project partners (MARVIC Glossary v1.0). The MARVIC Glossary v2.0 is publicly open to support broader efforts around carbon farming terminology. A user friendly glossary will be available on the website of MARVIC in a later phase.

The development process involved a literature review to identify existing definitions from official sources, which were then presented to the consortium for review when available. For terms without existing official definitions, the consortium discussed the identified concepts collaboratively, and added final, agreed-upon versions to the glossary. These definitions provide guidance for the consistent use of terminology in project reports and communications. Accordingly, the glossary cites either the consortium or an external source, depending on the origin of the definition.

To ensure ease of navigation, the glossary terms are grouped by the project's work packages (WPs) and categorized by thematic relevance, rather than listed alphabetically. Given the vast scope of carbon farming, this categorization was deemed more practical, with distinct categories such as practices, quantification, modelling, and certification, among others.

By consolidating and standardizing terminology, the MARVIC glossary supports a shared understanding within the consortium and lays the groundwork for improved communication and knowledge dissemination in the broader carbon farming community.

Table of Contents

Document information	i
Document revision history	ii
Project consortium	iii
Executive Summary	iv
Table of Contents.....	v
Abbreviations and Acronyms	vi
1. MRV methodology and administrative definitions (WP1).....	1
1.1 <i>Definitions related to certification</i>	1
1.2 <i>Definitions related to project organisation</i>	3
1.3 <i>Definitions related to the carbon pools and GHG emissions</i>	4
1.4 <i>Definitions on farming systems, soil and the environment</i>	6
2. Strategies for the smart use of diverse data sources, data acquisition techniques and tools to support MRV activities (WP2)	1
2.1 <i>Definitions related to sampling</i>	1
3. Modelling carbon sequestration and GHG fluxes (WP3)	2
3.1 <i>Definitions relating to the development and use of models</i>	2
4. Climate Metrics (WP4).....	6
4.1 <i>Definitions relating to radiative forcing</i>	6
5. Socio-economics & Politics (WP5).....	7
5.1 <i>Definitions relating to cost-effective carbon farming practices and MRV</i>	7
5.2 <i>Definitions relating to participatory policy design of MRV systems</i>	7
6. Bibliography	9

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AG	Grant Agreement
API	Application Programming Interface
ASE	Agricultural soil emissions
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CD&E	Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CF	Carbon Farming
CR	Carbon removals
EO	Earth Observation
FMIS	Farm management information systems
LPIS	Land Parcel Identification System
LSE	LULUCF soil emissions
OPC	Operational Processing Chain
RS	Remote sensing
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon

1. MRV methodology and administrative definitions (WP1)

1.1 Definitions related to certification

- **Carbon farming:** Any practice or process carried out over an activity period of at least five years, related to the management of a terrestrial or coastal environment and resulting in the capture and temporary storage of atmospheric or biogenic carbon in biogenic carbon pools, or in the reduction of soil emissions (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Carbon farming sequestration unit:** One metric tonne of CO₂ equivalent of certified temporary net carbon removal benefit generated by a carbon farming activity and registered by a certification scheme in its certification registry or, as applicable, in the Union registry provided for in Article 12 (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Carbon certificates:** carbon certificates equal 1 ton CO₂-eq that has been removed, avoided or reduced through the implementation of carbon farming practices, which preferably has been verified by an independent auditor. Carbon certificates do not allow companies to offset their emissions (use it in their carbon accounting) and declare itself carbon neutral. Carbon certificates allow companies to contribute to the decarbonization of their region/country (and make a positive contribution). Carbon certificates can be realized through local, regional or national/domestic carbon farming schemes or initiatives (e.g. Claire, Soil Capital, Label Bas Carbone, Stichting Nationale Koolstofmarkt). Contrary to carbon credits, carbon certificates cannot be traded internationally (own definition) (Annys, et al 2022)
- **Carbon credit:** Carbon credits equal 1 ton CO₂-eq that has been removed, avoided or reduced through the implementation of carbon farming practices, which preferably has been verified by an independent auditor. Carbon credits allow companies to offset their emissions (use it in their carbon accounting) and declare themselves carbon neutral. Carbon credits are realized through international carbon standards (e.g. Verified Carbon Standard, Gold Standard) endorsed by ICROA = the International Carbon Reduction & Offset Alliance. Contrary to carbon certificates, carbon credits can be traded internationally (own definition). (Annys, et al 2022)

- **Certificate of compliance:** A conformity statement issued by a certification body certifying that an activity complies with this Regulation, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Certification audit:** An audit carried out by a certification body, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Certification body:** An accredited or recognised independent conformity assessment body that has concluded an agreement with a certification scheme to carry out certification audits and issue certificates of compliance, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Certification period:** The period between a re-certification audit of an activity and the most recent preceding certification audit or re-certification audit of that activity, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Certification scheme:** An organisation that certifies the compliance of activities and operators with the quality criteria and certification rules set out in this Regulation, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Re-certification audit:** An audit carried out in the process of renewing a certificate of compliance issued by a certification body, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Scope 3:** Scope 3 emissions are a consequence of the activities of the company but occur from sources not owned or controlled by the company. Some examples of scope 3 activities are extraction and production of purchased materials; transportation of purchased fuels; and use of sold products and services. (World Business Council for Sustainable Development and World Resources Institute, 2004)
- **Insetting:** Insetting occurs when project outcomes are purchased by agrifood companies (within the value chain), which aim to reduce their scope 3 emissions (see section 7.1). This mostly occurs through the payment of price premiums (a higher price per production unit), rather than through the payment for carbon certificates / credits as such (own definition). Insetting claims are only valid under a rigorous set of conditions, including that the reductions and removals involved are additional, not over-estimated, and exclusively claimed. Further, insetting can only be used to claim net zero status to the extent it is “like for like” (see definition carbon neutrality) with any residual emissions (Race to Zero, 2021)
- **Offsetting:** Reducing GHG emissions (including through avoided emissions), or increasing GHG removals through activities external to an actor, in order to

compensate for GHG emissions, such that an actor's net contribution to global emissions is reduced. Offsetting is typically arranged through a marketplace for carbon credits or other exchange mechanism. Offsetting claims are only valid under a rigorous set of conditions, including that the reductions/removals involved are additional, not over-estimated, and exclusively claimed. Further, offsetting can only be used to claim net zero status to the extent it is “like for like” (see definition carbon neutrality) with any residual emissions (Race to Zero, 2021).

1.2 Definitions related to project organisation

- **Activity:** One or more practices or processes carried out by an operator, or a group of operators, resulting in a permanent carbon removal, a temporary carbon removal through carbon farming or through carbon storage in products, or soil emission reductions through carbon farming where such carbon farming, overall, reduces the emissions of carbon from soil carbon pools or increases carbon removals in biogenic carbon pools, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Activity area:** The spatially delimited area or areas where the activity takes place, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Activity period:** A period during which the activity generates a net carbon removal benefit or a net soil emission reduction benefit, and which is determined in the applicable certification methodology, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Agricultural Soil Emission (ASE):** Agricultural Soil Emission, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Group of operators:** A legal entity that represents at least two operators and is responsible for ensuring that those operators comply with this Regulation, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Operator:** Any natural or legal person or public entity that operates or controls an activity, or to whom decisive economic power over the technical functioning of the activity has been delegated; in the case of a carbon farming activity, ‘operator’ means a farmer as defined in Article 3(1) of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, any other manager of an activity in a terrestrial or coastal environment, a forest owner or manager as defined by national law, or a competent public entity, The CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012)
- **Monitoring period:** A period during which the soil emission reduction or storage of carbon is monitored by an operator or a group of operators, which covers at least the activity period, and which is determined in the applicable certification methodology , (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))

- **Renewal:** New activity period, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Field scale:** refers to the level of a field parcel (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Field parcel:** agricultural land parcel including its boundaries (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Plot scale:** refers to the sub-field level (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Project scale:** refers to the level of the project, which typically includes a set of parcels from a group of operators (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **LUST:** Land Use x Soil Types (LUST): MARVIC focuses on 1. arable farming on mineral soils, 2. permanent grassland on mineral soils (>5 year grassland), 3. agriculturally managed peatland, 4. woody crops/agroforestry (including orchards, hedges and small wood lots) (MARVIC Consortium, 2025)

1.3 Definitions related to the carbon pools and GHG emissions

- **ASEbaseline:** The amount of agricultural soil emissions under the baseline , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **ASEtotal:**, The total amount of agricultural soil emissions of the activity, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Biogenic carbon pool:** Living biomass, litter, deadwood, dead organic matter, mineral soils and organic soils as listed in Section B, points (a) to (f), of Annex I to Regulation (EU) 2018/841, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **CRbaseline:** The amount of carbon removals under the baseline , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **CRtotal:** The total amount of carbon removals of the activity, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **GHG associated:** The increase in direct and indirect greenhouse gas emissions over the entire lifecycle of the activity which are attributable to its implementation, including indirect land use change, calculated, where applicable, in accordance with the protocols set forth in the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories and any further refinement to these 2006 IPCC Guidelines , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **LSE:** LULUCF Soil Emission , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))

- **LSEbaseline:** The amount of LULUCF soil emissions under the baseline , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **LSEtotal:** The total amount of LULUCF soil emissions of the activity, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Net soil emission reduction benefit:** $LSE_{baseline} - LSE_{total} + ASE_{baseline} - ASE_{total} - GHG_{associated} > 0$, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Soil emission reduction:** The reduction of net greenhouse gas emissions from biogenic carbon pools as listed in Section B, points (e) and (f), of Annex I to Regulation (EU) 2018/841 or the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from the IPCC source category of agriculture, subcategory 3.D agricultural soils, as determined pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2018/1999, where the relevant activity, overall, reduces the emission of carbon from soil carbon pools or increases carbon removals in biogenic carbon pools, (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Soil emission reduction unit:** One metric tonne of CO₂ equivalent of certified net soil emission reduction benefit generated by a carbon farming activity and registered by a certification scheme in its certification registry or, as applicable, in the Union registry provided for in Article 12 , (CRCF regulation (EU 2024/3012))
- **Temporary net carbon removal benefit:** $CR_{baseline} - CR_{total} - GHG_{associated} > 0$, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **C sequestration in soils:** Process of transferring C from the atmosphere into the soil through plants or other organisms, which is retained as soil organic carbon resulting in a global C stock increase of the soil (Don et al, 2023, based on IPCC, 2001; Olson et al.,2014)
- **SOC loss mitigation:** An anthropogenic intervention to reduce SOC losses compared to a business-as-usual scenario (Don et al, 2023)
- **Negative emission:** Net removal of CO₂-equivalents of greenhouse gases from the atmosphere (Don et al, 2023)
- **SOC storage:** The size of the SOC pool (i.e., SOC stock or SOC content) (Don et al, 2023)
- **SOC accrual:** An increase in SOC stock at a given unit of land, starting from an initial SOC stock or compared to a business-as-usual value (does not always result in climate change mitigation or C sequestration in soils (Don et al, 2023)

1.4 Definitions on farming systems, soil and the environment

- **Mineral soil:** Soil that is not organic soil , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Natural disturbance event:** An event or series of events resulting from natural processes, such as wildfires, storms, extreme climate events, or biological and insect outbreaks, that lead to significant alterations in the structure and functioning of ecosystems., (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Organic soil:** Organic soil as established in accordance with the 2006 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Guidelines¹ ('2006 IPCC Guidelines') or under national definitions accepted under greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories reporting, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Peat:** A layer of soil that primarily consists of partially decomposed plant material, that has accumulated under conditions of waterlogging, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Peat depletion time:** A time period over which the total peat layer would disappear in the absence of the activity , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Water table:** The height of a phreatic water surface relative to the soil surface , (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Agroforestry:** Agroforestry includes all types of agricultural systems, in which an agricultural component, either arable land, grassland and/or livestock, is combined and interacts with woody perennials like trees, hedges, or shrubs,(MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Silvopastoral:** A system that combines, on the same plot, woody perennials (trees, hedges or shrubs), a pasture or other forage cover, and the grazing of animals (most often ruminants), managed in a way to produce both timber/trees and livestock,(MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Silvoarable:** A system that combines, on the same plot, woody perennials (trees, hedges or shrubs), and annual or perennial crops (cereals, protein crops, etc.), with joint management of both the tree and crop components,(MARVIC Consortium, 2025).

2. Strategies for the smart use of diverse data sources, data acquisition techniques and tools to support MRV activities (WP2)

2.1 Definitions related to sampling

- **Sampling:** The process of selecting units from a population to estimate characteristics of the whole population. (Brus, 2022)
- **Sample size:** The number of units in the sample is referred to as the sample size. (Brus, 2022)
- **Sampling unit:** A sampling unit is an element or a group of elements considered for selection in some stage of sampling. (Brus, 2022)
- **Sampling position:** The specific point or area within the study region where a sample is collected. (Brus, 2022)
- **Sampling location:** The geographic coordinates or area where the sampling unit is located. (Brus, 2022)
- **Minimum Detectable Difference (MDD):** The smallest difference between population parameters can be detected with a given level of confidence and power. (Brus, 2022)
- **Confidence interval:** A range of values, derived from the sample statistics, that is likely to contain the value of an unknown population parameter. (Brus, 2022)
- **Composite sample:** A sample obtained by combining several individual samples, often to reduce analytical costs or to obtain an average measure. (Brus, 2022)
- **Sampling design:** The method or plan used to select sampling units from the population. (Brus, 2022)
- **Standard error:** A measure of the statistical accuracy of an estimate, indicating the variability of the estimate due to sampling. (Brus, 2022)
- **Stratification:** The process of dividing a population into subgroups (strata) that are more homogeneous. (Brus, 2022)

3. Modelling carbon sequestration and GHG fluxes (WP3)

3.1 Definitions relating to the development and use of models

- **Benchmark sites:** Umbrella definition for reference locations where soil, vegetation and management data are collected with sufficient detail and/or continuity to support our understanding of SOC dynamics in agricultural systems (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Model conceptualisation:** Definition of the conceptual model describing the system of interest, that identifies the processes to be modelled and defines the mathematical relationships and parameters that simulate real-world processes (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Model domain of validity:** For a model to be considered suitable for usage in an MRV system over an area of interest, it must be suitably calibrated and validated for the LUST(s), pedoclimatic areas, CF practices, and crops of interest in that area. The model domain is defined as the combination of LUSTs, pedoclimatic areas, CF practices, and crops that the model has been suitably calibrated/validated on (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Model parametrization:** The set of parameter values chosen are deemed suitable for model use in the specific domain of interest (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Calibration:** A process involving the adjustment of parameters and constants within a model so that it predicts the measured values more accurately, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Validation:** The process of evaluating the performance of a model with regard to measured values, demonstrating its satisfactory performance in terms of suitability and characterisation of model prediction error, (CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026))
- **Model testing:** Testing the model in a new domain to verify if it can be used/is valid without further calibration/validation by assessing its performance on a new set of data (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **State variables:** The set of variables that determines the state of the dynamic system at the start of the project (T0) (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).

- **Model initialization:** Process of setting the model state variables to reflect the initial state at the start of the model simulation. Usually conducted during a so-called model “spin-up phase” (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Model prediction error:** Uncertainty in model predictions, as determined from comparison to direct measurements. Measurements used to determine model prediction error must be the same as those used to validate the model (Verra VCS, 2023).
- **Environmental zones (standardized pedoclimatic area of Europe):** Classification, or stratification, of European land into strata of relatively homogeneous climate, geology, geomorphology, soils, vegetation and land cover (Metzger *et al.*, 2012).
- **Pedoclimatic area:** Geographical areas of relatively homogenous soil type and climate conditions (MARVIC Consortium, 2025).
- **Model level 1:** Empirical models represent observed relationships between SOC changes and environmental, or environmental and management practices. Can be regression-based or can implement machine-learning techniques when solid domain knowledge is available (Biffi *et al.*, 2025).
- **Model level 2:** Soil process models that simulate SOC dynamics from SOM turnover, considering the effects of climate, soil factors, land use, and management (e.g. C-TOOL, Roth-C, ICBM) (Biffi *et al.*, 2025).
- **Model level 3:** Ecosystem models that also integrate feedback from multiple soil-plant-atmospheric processes (e.g. STICS, DAYCENT, Landscape DNDC, APSIM) (Biffi *et al.*, 2025).
- **Crop categories:** Groupings of “similar” crops that could be used interchangeably in the arable LUST when model calibration for the specific crop type and carbon farming practice is not possible (Biffi *et al.*, 2025).
- **Model Suitability check:** Ensuring a model's transparency, openness, and pre-existing testing to verify its use without calibration and validation. If a documented, version-controlled, and publicly available model has been successfully tested in scientific publications for a specific Pedoclimate × Crop category, it can be used directly (Biffi *et al.*, 2025).
- **Operational Processing Chain (OPC):** Automated workflow that connects data (e.g. land cover, weather or soil property maps, statistics, farm data, remote sensing data) and models via automated workflows to quantify and assess accuracy of soil organic carbon stock changes, carbon budget components (e.g. biomass, CO₂ fluxes) and soil GHG emission. An OPC can contain one model (e.g. a soil model using databases for biomass production input) or several

models (e.g. a soil model taking biomass data input from a crop model driven by satellite data, several soil models providing an ensemble of simulations). (MARVIC Consortium, 2025)

- **Data assimilation:** Process of integrating observational data into models (e.g. process-based) to enhance the accuracy of simulations and reduce uncertainty of predictions while ensuring the consistency between modelled outputs and observed data. Most commonly, this technique is applied in crop models (e.g., WOFOST, APSIM, SAFYE-CO₂), with satellite-derived data to improve estimates of key biogeophysical variables like biomass, yield, and soil moisture. Various assimilation methods exist, including sequential (e.g., Ensemble Kalman Filter), variational (e.g., 4DVAR), calibration-based, and other probabilistic approaches (e.g., MCMC Bayesian inference). While remote sensing data is the primary source of observational inputs, other data, such as CO₂ flux measurements, can also be assimilated to refine model predictions. Assimilation of RS data allows a more objective accounting of biomass spatial variability (and carbon inputs to the soil) while relaxing the need for some input data (e.g. date of sowing, fertilisation) since the data assimilation process allows to implicitly account for some practices, stresses (nitrogen, water), extreme events (e.g. hail, floods), spontaneous regrowth, etc. impacting vegetation development (MARVIC Consortium, 2025)
- **Modelling workflow:** All the steps required for preparing and running one or more models to produce model predictions. This includes input data curation, model configuration and parametrization, initialisation, spin-up, and post-processing (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Project modelling:** Running an OPC for a Project over a specific Project area, under specific farming conditions, and using relevant data layers (i.e. using an MRV tool across one or multiple farms) (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **MRV modelling workflow:** In an MRV system, sequence of actions that are directly linked to running a model (or multiple models) using a modelling workflow (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Uncertainty:** The state of incomplete knowledge about the value of a quantity or the magnitude of an error. Statistically, uncertainty is represented by a probability distribution over the quantity (or over its error), reflecting which values are considered possible and how likely they are. Uncertainty can be summarized by measures such as standard deviations, confidence or credible intervals, and prediction intervals. This measure corresponds to the UNC (uncertainty

deduction factor) in the CRCF annexes to the Delegated Act (draft carbon farming methodology, January 2026)(MARVIC Consortium, 2026)

- **Error:** Refers to the difference between the measured (measurement error) or estimated (model error) value and the true (but unknown) value of the SOC stock (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Model error:** Can be decomposed into **input-data error** and **process (structural) error**. Model input-data error arises because model inputs (e.g. initial conditions, weather drivers, soil properties, parameters) have measurement errors of their own which propagate through the model. Process (structural) error arises when important processes are missing, oversimplified, or misrepresented in the model and can be defined as the remaining error if all inputs were to be known perfectly. Similar to measurement error, model error can also be thought to have a third **representativeness error** component which can be framed as the wrong domain of applicability (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Precision:** The degree to which repeated measurements or estimates of the same quantity under the same conditions yield similar values; the closer the values, the higher the precision. High precision means low dispersion (low variance) of the error term. Precision is determined by stochastic (random) error and is conceptually independent of accuracy: for instance, measurements can be precise but systematically wrong, or imprecise but, on average, unbiased (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Variability:** The presence of real differences in the true value of a quantity across space, time, or units. Variability is a property of the system, not the measurement device. It is typically summarized by the variance or standard deviation of the true values. More data improve our characterization of variability but do not reduce it. When measurements are precise there will be little uncertainty about variability in the sample (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)
- **Measurement error:** Can be decomposed into stochastic (random) measurement error and systematic measurement error. Stochastic error refers to the random noise (small-scale fluctuations), it has to do with how accurate any single measurement is and can be reduced by more replicates. Systematic measurement error is a consistent bias (e.g. miscalibration or systematic sampling bias), which shifts measurements up or down. It affects accuracy and cannot be reduced by mere replication; it requires improved calibration, instruments or protocols. Measurement error can also be thought to have a third component called the representativeness error which is the mismatch between where/how you measure and what the true quantity actually

presents, however this can be framed as a sampling design issue (MARVIC Consortium, 2026)

4. Climate Metrics (WP4)

4.1 Definitions relating to radiative forcing

- **Absolute Global Warming Potential (AGWP):** A metric measuring the radiative forcing following an emission of a unit mass of a given substance, accumulated over a chosen time horizon. (Adapted from IPCC, 2021)
- **Project AGWP:** A measure of the radiative forcing resulting from a Project Intervention, accumulated over a chosen time horizon. (MARVIC Consortium, 2025)
- **Switchover time:** The length of time after which the positive radiative forcing due to increases in CH₄ emissions at a restored wetland is overtaken by the cumulative negative radiative forcing due to CO₂ uptake. (Hemes et al., 2019)
- **Albedo:** The proportion of incoming solar radiation that is reflected by a surface or object, sometimes expressed as a percentage but more generally ranging from 0 (all incoming solar radiation is absorbed) to 1 (all is reflected back towards space). (IPCC, 2021)
- **Absolute Global Temperature-change Potential (AGTP):** A metric measuring the global mean surface temperature change at a chosen time horizon, following an emission of a unit mass of a given substance or a change in surface albedo. (Boucher et al., 2009)
- **Project AGTP:** A measure of the global mean surface temperature change at a chosen time horizon resulting from a Project Intervention. (MARVIC Consortium, 2025)
- **Airborne fraction:** The fraction of total carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (from fossil fuels and land-use change) remaining in the atmosphere. (IPCC, 2021)
- **Simple climate model:** A broad class of lower dimensional models of the energy balance, radiative transfer, carbon cycle, or a combination of such physical components. (IPCC, 2021)
- **Adjustment time:** In the context of lifetimes, adjustment time is the time scale characterizing the decay of an instantaneous pulse input into the reservoir. (IPCC, 2021)
- **Permanence:** Sustained storage of the sequestered carbon in the long term (>1000 years). (according to Allen et al, 2022; Allend et al, 2025 and Solomon et al, 2009).
- **Climate change mitigation:** An anthropogenic intervention that reduces the sources or enhance the sinks of greenhouse gases (Don et al, 2023 based on IPCC, 2021)

- **Climate benefit:** Avoided energy accumulation in the Earth System or avoided global warming at a given point in time. (MARVIC consortium, 2025)
- **Radiative Forcing:** it is a concept used to quantify the change in energy balance of the Earth's atmosphere. Various factors contribute to this change, such as concentrations of GHG and aerosols, or changes in surface albedo and solar irradiance. (MARVIC consortium, 2025)

5. Socio-economics & Politics (WP5)

5.1 Definitions relating to cost-effective carbon farming practices and MRV

- **Opportunity cost:** The benefits that would have been obtained if the input resources had been used in the second most beneficial activity. (MARVIC Consortium, 2025)
- **Public/private transaction cost:** Private costs are those that accrue to private agents (households, farms, firms), public costs are those that accrue to governments at different levels. (MARVIC Consortium, 2025)

5.2 Definitions relating to participatory policy design of MRV systems

- **Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) :** Model to predict and explain human behaviour. It suggests that intentions are central to performing a behaviour. Intentions are influenced by:
 - 1. Attitude toward the behaviour
 - 2. Subjective norm
 - 3. Perceived behavioural control.Actual behaviour is contingent on volitional control and the availability of opportunities and resources. (Ajzen, 1991)
- **Policy coherence (PC):** Attribute of policy that systematically reduces conflicts/trade-offs and promotes synergies between and within different policy areas to achieve the outcomes associated with jointly agreed policy objectives. (Nilsson et al., 2012)
- **Attitude toward behaviour :** Positive or negative evaluation of a behaviour. (Ajzen, 1985)
- **Subjective norm:** Perceived social pressure to perform or not perform a behaviour. (Ajzen, 1991)

- ***Perceived behavioural control:*** Perceived ease or difficulty of performing a behaviour, influenced by factors such as expected obstacles, access to resources, and previous experience. (Ajzen, 1985, 1991)
- ***Social desirability bias:*** Indicates tendency or respondents to bias their answers in a survey to appear in a more favourable light. (Crowne & Marlowe, 1960)

6. Bibliography

Ajzen, I. (1985). From Intentions to Actions: A Theory of Planned Behavior. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-69746-3_2

Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)

Allen, M. R., Friedlingstein, P., Girardin, C. A., Jenkins, S., Malhi, Y., Mitchell-Larson, E., ... & Rajamani, L. (2022). Net zero: science, origins, and implications. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), 849-887. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-112320-105050>

Allen, M.R., Frame, D.J., Friedlingstein, P. et al. Geological Net Zero and the need for disaggregated accounting for carbon sinks. *Nature* 638, 343–350 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08326-8>

Anny, S., Facq, E., Beirinckx, S., Lemeire, E., & Ruyschaert, G. (2022). A system analysis of carbon farming schemes in support of the wider implementation of carbon farming in Flanders (Belgium).

Boucher, O., Friedlingstein, P., Collins, B., & Shine, K. P. (2009). The indirect global warming potential and global temperature change potential due to methane oxidation. *Environmental Research Letters*, 4, 044007. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/4/4/044007>

Brus, D. J. (2022). *Spatial Sampling with R*. Chapman and Hall/CRC. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003258940>

Crowne, D. P., & Marlowe, D. (1960). A new scale of social desirability independent of psychopathology. *Journal of Consulting Psychology*, 24(4), 349-354. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0047358>

Don, A., Seidel, F., Leifeld, J., Kätterer, T., Martin, M., Pellerin, S., ... & Chenu, C. (2024). Carbon sequestration in soils and climate change mitigation—Definitions and pitfalls. *Global Change Biology*, 30(1), e16983. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16983>

Hemes, K. S., Chamberlain, S. D., Eichelmann, E., Anthony, T., Valach, A., Kasak, K., Szutu, D., Verfaillie, J., Silver, W. L., & Baldocchi, D. D. (2019). Assessing the carbon and climate benefit of restoring degraded agricultural peat soils to managed wetlands. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 268, 202-214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2019.01.017>

IPCC, 2021: Annex VII: Glossary [Matthews, J.B.R., V. Möller, R. van Diemen, J.S. Fuglestvedt, V. Masson-Delmotte, C. Méndez, S. Semenov, A. Reisinger (eds.)]. In Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 2215–2256, doi:10.1017/9781009157896.02

MARVIC Consortium. (2025). Consortium Agreement Definition.

Nilsson, M., Zamparutti, T., Petersen, J. E., Nykvist, B., Rudberg, P., & McGuinn, J. (2012). Understanding Policy Coherence : Analytical Framework and Examples of Sector–Environment Policy Interactions in the EU. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 22(6), 395-423. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1589>

Olson, K. R., Al-Kaisi, M. M., Lal, R., & Lowery, B. (2014). Experimental consideration, treatments, and methods in determining soil or-ganic carbon sequestration rates. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 78(2), 348–360. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2013.09.041>

Race to Zero (2021) Race to Zero Lexicon. *Race-to-Zero-Lexicon.pdf* (unfccc.int). Consulted: May 18, 2022.

World Resources Institute & World Business Council for Sustainable Development. (2004). The greenhouse gas protocol: A corporate accounting and reporting standard (Revised edition). https://ghgprotocol.org/sites/default/files/standards_supporting/ghg-protocol-revised.pdf

Solomon, S., Plattner, G. K., Knutti, R., & Friedlingstein, P. (2009). Irreversible climate change due to carbon dioxide emissions. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 106(6), 1704-1709. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0812721106>

MARVIC
MRV for carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union